

Synthesis of Some Substituted Anthraquinone and Acridine Derivatives and Their Antiamebic Activities

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In our attempt to synthesize new compounds with antiamebic activities, some substituted anthraquinone and acridine derivatives have been made. The compounds have been subjected to *in vitro* screening using axenic cultures of *E. histolytica*. The compounds have been found to be more effective than 5-chloro-7-iodo-8-quinolinol but less effective than metronidazole.

AMEBIASIS is one of the most prevalent diseases in tropical countries. A number of useful drugs like emetine hydrochloride, iodo-chlorohydroxyquinoline and metronidazole are known but they are usually associated with adverse side effects¹⁻³. Metronidazole is at present the primary drug in the treatment of amebiasis^{3,4}. But its toxic effects like cardiotoxicity⁵ and malignancy^{6,7} in the rodents have been reported. Thus, the search for new antiamebic drugs is urgently felt.

Many 1-substituted 4- or 5-imidazole derivatives have activity against *T. vaginalis*, *T. foetus*⁸ as well as against *E. histolytica*. A monoformamide of 2-aminoanthraquinone, reported to have antiparasitic activity⁹, was inactive as amebicide. However, a series of bisamidines of 2,6-diaminoanthraquinone were found to be effective against cecal and hepatic forms of *E. histolytica* infections in rats and hamsters, respectively¹⁰. 2,6-Bis(1-piperidinoalkylidene-amino)anthraquinone exhibited amebicidal activity¹¹. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the antiamebic activities of substituted anthraquinone compounds (Table 1) where the basic group is kept one *c*-atom away from the anthraquinone moiety. Some of the compounds may be considered to be modified imidazole derivatives. Insecticidal, bactericidal, antimalarial and local anaesthetic properties are exhibited by acridine derivatives¹²⁻¹⁶. The flat aromatic acridine molecule was thought to be inserted (*i.e.* intercalated) between adjacent base pairs in the double helix of DNA and the intercalating compounds inhibit DNA synthesis and DNA dependent RNA synthesis in microbial cells¹⁷. Synthesis of some 9-substituted acridine derivatives (Table 1) was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study their amebicidal properties.

The synthesis and *in vitro* antiamebic activities of some substituted anthraquinone and 9-substituted

acridine derivatives using axenic cultures of *E. histolytica* have been reported in this communication.

Experimental

Biological activity: The *in vitro* testing of the compounds was done using axenic medium. In bacteria-associated culture of *E. histolytica*, the amebicidal activity of a test compound is influenced by various factors such as media, pH, oxidation-reduction potential and the bacterial flora. The variations of amebicidal end point are likely to occur in different non-axenic cultures. True chemotherapeutic activities of amebicidal agents could be made using the axenic culture of *E. histolytica*. The composition of the axenic medium was similar to that of TP-S-1 monophasic medium¹⁸.

We, however, eliminated horse serum (or bovine serum as used¹⁹) as well as ascorbic acid. The bacterial flora was eradicated by treatment with gentian violet and acriflavine²⁰. Sufficient NaOH (1*N*) was added to the broth to adjust the pH 7 or a little above. The broth was autoclaved and stored at 4°. However, the use of antibiotics was avoided.

E. histolytica (L. D. strain) was grown axenically in modified TP-S-1 Diamond medium. The screw cap corning tubes (12 ml) containing 8.8 ml of the medium were incubated at 37° for 24 h to check the sterility of the medium. For ameba culture and drug testing, the reported^{21,22} method was followed.

Ten days old cultures initiated from small inocula was used as seeds for inoculum. These were chilled in ice-cold water for 5 min, gently stirred and centrifuged at slow speed. The supernatant fluid was decanted off, leaving the residue in the medium in which the ameba were homogenised and counted several times with haemocytometer and the average taken.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION DATA ON 2-SUBSTITUTED ANTHRAQUINONE AND 9-SUBSTITUTED ACRIDIDE

Sl. no.	Compound	Method of prepn.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % ; Found / (Calcd.)			Uv spectra (EtOH) λ_{max} (Log ϵ) nm	Minimum inhibitory concn. $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
					C	H	N		
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>(IB Series)</p> </div> </div>									
IA Series									
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1.	N(CH ₃) ₂	A	90–92	40	76.60 (76.98)	5.35 (5.66)	5.12 (5.28)	256 (4.57) 326–27 (3.57)	31.3
2.	N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	A	75–78	45	77.40 (77.80)	6.24 (6.48)	4.52 (4.77)	256 (4.59) 326–27 (3.60)	15.6
3.	piperidyl	A	103–105	40	78.48 (78.68)	6.05 (6.23)	4.45 (4.59)	256 (4.63) 326–328 (3.66)	62.5
4.	morpholinyl	A	100–101	30	74.04 (74.27)	5.32 (5.54)	4.26 (4.56)	256 (4.59) 326–328 (3.69)	15.6
5.	imidazolyl	B	188–190	38	74.88 (75.01)	3.85 (4.17)	9.64 (9.72)	256 (4.49) 324–326 (3.66)	31.3
6.	5-nitroimidazolyl	B	249–251	35	63.64 (63.88)	3.10 (3.30)	12.42 (12.61)	254 (4.55) 318–322 (3.78)	15.6
7.	2-methylimidazolyl	B	165–166	40	75.25 (75.50)	4.52 (4.63)	8.95 (9.27)	254 (4.49) 305–310 (3.86)	15.6
8.	2-methyl-5-nitroimidazolyl	B	238–240	25	65.65 (65.70)	3.62 (3.75)	11.95 (12.11)	254 (4.50) 305–310 (3.87)	62.5
IB Series									
9.	–imidazolyl	C	334–335	20	77.94 (78.36)	4.35 (4.49)	16.90 (17.14)	253 (4.80) 379 (2.92) 397 (3.90)	62.5
10.	5-nitroimidazolyl	C	337° (volatile)	20	65.98 (66.21)	3.23 (3.45)	19.12 (19.32)	253 (4.89) 380 (3.17) 398 (3.98)	15.6
11.	2-methylimidazolyl	C	219–221	25	78.65 (78.75)	4.98 (5.02)	15.96 (16.21)	251 (5.02) 359 (3.95) 383 (3.66)	31.3
12.	2-methyl-5-nitroimidazolyl	C	241–243	22	67.05 (67.10)	3.85 (3.95)	18.21 (18.42)	251 (4.08) 300–302 (3.95)	31.3
13.	5-chloro-7-iodo-8-quinolinol	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	62.5
14.	Metronidazole	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	3.9

Seven days' old culture was used as inoculum and the tubes containing $\sim 20 \times 10^4$ amebae ml^{-1} were used for drug testing. 0.2 ml amebic suspension was used for inoculation. 1 ml drug suspension in normal saline was added to 9 ml (containing 8.8 ml of medium + 0.2 of inoculum) in each culture tube in duplicate to give a drug concentration $1000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Eight successive two fold serial dilutions of the drug in normal saline were made and the drugs were added in the way described before in subsequent duplicate tubes. Strict aseptic condition was maintained. Drug dilutions were sterilized by autoclaving at 10 lbs/sq. inch for 15 min before test. The tests were run for 48 h and incubation carried out at 37°.

The cultures were examined after 48 h for viable and motile amebae and amebicidal end points were noted. The results were further confirmed by sub-culture. The operations were repeated for confirming the reproducibility of results.

Preparation and characterization of compounds: The uv spectra of the compounds were recorded with Perkin-Elmer-Hitachi 200 spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined using Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

2-Bromomethylantraquinone (m.p. 200–205°) was prepared from 2-methylantraquinone by the action of *N*-bromosuccinimide and traces of benzoyl peroxide in dry CCl_4 . The 2-bromomethylantraquinone was then allowed to react with the appropriate amine by the following methods.

Method A: Equimolar bromo-compound and the amine were refluxed on water bath for 4 h in sealed tubes and the content were then poured in water. The solid compound separated was dissolved in dilute HCl, extracted with ether and the acidic solution was basified with liquor NH_3 . The compound separated was washed with water, dried and crystallized from dilute alcohol.

Method B: Equimolar halo-compound and the imidazole derivative were dissolved in minimum volume of DMF and the solution was kept on boiling water bath for 3 h and then in oil bath so that DMF boiled gently. Finally it was acidified with dilute HCl and extracted with ether. Aqueous acidic solution was basified with liquor NH₃ when a solid separated. The solid was filtered out, washed with water, dried and the product was crystallized from dilute alcohol.

Method C: A mixture of 9-chloroacridine and imidazole derivative (0.005 mol each) was refluxed with phenol (5 ml) in an oil bath for 24 h. The mass was then acidified with dilute HCl, phenol was extracted out with ether, the aqueous acid layer was basified with liquor NH₃ and the material was filtered out. The product was crystallized from alcohol.

The characterization data of the compounds, their absorption maxima and antiamebic end points are recorded in the Table 1. *In vitro* antiamebic end points of some typical drugs in axenic medium were also recorded for comparison. The absorption maxima contains the characteristic bands of athraquinone and acridine molecules which shifted towards the long wavelength region.

Discussion

The reasons for the antiamebic activities of the compounds are not known. But the reasons may be due to penetration of these water insoluble compounds into the protozoal cells. It is also known that the compounds which have shown to bind the DNA by intercalation have generally been condensed tricyclic aromatics with atleast one basic function^{24,25}. Thus, the activities of the compounds may be due to binding of DNA by intercalation though we could not adduce sufficient evidence in favour of this hypothesis.

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